

Incomplete Lemierre Syndrome: A Fusobacterium Induced Sepsis in a Middle-Aged Male

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ABSTRACT

Lemierre syndrome (LS) is a rare, life-threatening condition characterized by septic thrombophlebitis of the internal jugular vein (IJV), typically following an oropharyngeal infection with *Fusobacterium necrophorum*. We present a previously healthy 41-year-old male who developed *Fusobacterium*-induced sepsis without radiologically confirmed internal jugular vein thrombosis. The patient presented with altered mental status, systemic inflammatory response, and right upper extremity edema. Imaging revealed multiple bilateral pulmonary nodules and subcutaneous emphysema. Despite the absence of radiologically confirmed IJV thrombosis, blood and wound cultures confirmed *F. necrophorum* infection, establishing the diagnosis of LS. The patient required intensive care, broad-spectrum antibiotics, and surgical intervention, ultimately recovering with targeted antimicrobial therapy. This case highlights an atypical “incomplete” LS presentation, emphasizing the need for high clinical suspicion, early diagnosis, and prompt treatment to reduce morbidity and mortality.

Keywords: Lemierre syndrome; *Fusobacterium necrophorum*; Septic thrombophlebitis; Internal jugular vein thrombosis; Oropharyngeal infection; Septicemia; Atypical Lemierre syndrome; Septicaemia

INTRODUCTION

Lemierre syndrome (LS) is a rare and life-threatening condition characterized by septic thrombophlebitis of the internal jugular vein (IJV), typically following an oropharyngeal infection. *Fusobacterium necrophorum*, an anaerobic Gram-negative bacillus, is the most common causative agent. The syndrome classically presents with pharyngitis or lateral neck pain, progressing to septicemia and metastatic infections. Diagnosis is often supported by contrast-enhanced computed tomography (CT) of the neck, which reveals jugular vein thrombosis, and confirmed by anaerobic blood cultures.^[1]

LS is commonly seen in healthy young adults, with an annual incidence of 14.4 cases per million people aged 15–24 years. Reports also note LS in children and the elderly, although less commonly. There is a male predominance in LS, with a 2:1 male-to-female ratio for reasons that remain unclear.^[2]

The diagnosis of LS involves identifying deep neck infections followed by septicemia, thrombophlebitis of the internal jugular vein, and metastatic infections with septic emboli.^[2] Isolation of *F. necrophorum* may be an early diagnostic clue, but culture results may take days, during which metastatic disease can progress. Imaging, particularly contrast-enhanced CT, is crucial for diagnosing LS, as it can visualize internal jugular vein thrombosis and metastatic lesions. Doppler ultrasound, although less sensitive, can detect jugular vein thrombosis. MRI is another alternative for diagnosis but is limited by cost and availability.^[3]

Empiric treatment of LS includes beta-lactamase-resistant antibiotics targeting *F. necrophorum* and oral streptococci, such as piperacillin-tazobactam, carbapenems, or ceftriaxone plus metronidazole. For severe cases or when methicillin-resistant *S. aureus* (MRSA) infection is suspected, vancomycin should be added. If central nervous system involvement is present, vancomycin, ceftriaxone, and metronidazole may be used. Once culture results confirm *F. necrophorum* and clinical improvement is evident, therapy may be narrowed to metronidazole. Antibiotic treatment typically lasts at least four weeks, with adjustments based on the clinical course.^[1]

This case report provides a unique perspective on Lemierre syndrome, showcasing an atypical presentation in a middle-aged male with no prior medical history. The patient's clinical course highlights the diagnostic challenges associated with incomplete Lemierre syndrome, characterized by the absence of radiologically confirmed internal jugular vein thrombosis.^[4] Instead, metastatic infections and septicemia dominated the clinical picture. By documenting this case, we aim to contribute to the growing body of literature exploring the diverse presentations of Lemierre syndrome, emphasizing the importance of clinical suspicion, early diagnosis, and tailored management strategies to optimize patient outcomes.

CASE PRESENTATION

A 41-year-old African American male with no known past medical history presented to the emergency department with altered mental status (AMS), 2 weeks history of flu-like symptoms, and multiple dental procedures in the past 3 months. He was diaphoretic, febrile, tachycardic, and tachypneic with extensive right upper extremity (RUE) edema, tenderness, and decreased range of motion. On physical examination, abdominal distention, anasarca, jaundice, and scleral icterus were noted. Lung auscultation revealed decreased breath sounds bilaterally. Laboratory results demonstrated neutrophilic leucocytosis, high lipase, elevated LFTs with hyperbilirubinemia, elevated BUN, creatinine, ESR, and CRP. Initial chest X-ray showed multiple lung nodules (Figure 1). CT revealed hepatosplenomegaly and multiple bilateral lung nodules with ground glass attenuation as shown in Figure 2. Non-contrast CT brain imaging was unremarkable. RUE ultrasound showed diffuse edema.

Figure 1: Initial Chest X ray showing notable lung nodules (yellow arrows)

Figure 2: Initial non-contrast computed tomography (CT) of the chest showing multiple lung nodules (yellow arrows)

The patient was admitted to the ICU for sepsis and started on empiric intravenous antibiotics (vancomycin and ceftriaxone). During intubation, airway examination revealed a purulent, bloody, and friable left-sided oropharyngeal collection, highly suggestive of an abscess. On repeat physical examination, subcutaneous emphysema and crepitus were noted in the RUE. A non-contrast CT scan of the RUE (Figure 3) confirmed multiple air pockets. Given concerns for necrotizing fasciitis, orthopaedic surgery was consulted, and the patient underwent an urgent fasciotomy with washout within the first 24 hours. Intraoperatively, multiple pus-filled clusters were identified within the arm. Antibiotics regimens were escalated to linezolid, clindamycin, and meropenem, and deep wound cultures were obtained. Due to worsening renal function, a contrast-enhanced CT of the neck was deferred. A non-contrast CT was performed but did not reveal internal jugular vein (IJV) thrombosis. A transesophageal echocardiogram was negative for endocarditis. Bronchoscopy with bronchoalveolar lavage was performed, and samples were sent for analysis. Blood cultures obtained on admission grew *Fusobacterium necrophorum* on hospital day six. Notably, deep wound cultures from the surgical debridement on day four also yielded the same organism, confirming a diagnosis of Lemierre's syndrome.

Consequently, antibiotic therapy was adjusted to ampicillin-sulbactam (3g IV every 6 hours). The remainder of the hospital course was unremarkable, and the patient was discharged home.

Figure 3: CT Right upper extremities non-contrast showing the right upper extremity (RUE) with several air pockets (red arrows).

DISCUSSION

Lemierre Syndrome (LS), also referred to as post-anginal sepsis and necrobacillosis, was described by André Lemierre in 1936.^[1,2] The clinical features described in his work laid the groundwork for what is now referred to as Lemierre syndrome. He reported cases of patients who developed septicemia due to anaerobic organisms, particularly *Fusobacterium necrophorum*. He noted the presence of local thrombophlebitis and metastatic septic lesions following primary infections. However, there is no consensus on a standardized definition of LS, with different authors using varying criteria. Some definitions limit the primary infection to the oropharynx, while others include broader sources. Similarly, some criteria restrict the infectious organisms to *Fusobacterium* species, while others require radiologically proven jugular vein thrombosis or the presence of metastatic septic emboli instead.^[2]

Fusobacterium necrophorum is the primary organism responsible for LS, though some infections are caused by polymicrobial bacteremia. *F. necrophorum* is a Gram-negative anaerobic rod that is part of the normal oral flora but becomes pathogenic under certain conditions, penetrating the mucosa and causing infection. Mucosal damage during bacterial or viral infections, particularly infectious mononucleosis, is thought to facilitate this invasion.^[1,5] The primary source of infection includes the tonsils and peritonsillar tissue, with less common sources being the lungs, middle ear, mastoid bone, teeth, and sinuses.^[5] Local invasion of the infection into the lateral pharyngeal space can lead to septic thrombophlebitis of the internal jugular vein. Potential mechanisms include hematogenous spread through the tonsillar vein, direct invasion of the peritonsillar region, or lymphatic extension into the adjacent lateral pharyngeal space.^[1] Metastatic infections occur in 63%–100% of patients. The lungs are the most common site of metastasis, followed by major joints, with additional reports of infection in the liver, muscle, pericardium, brain, and skin.^[5]

Patients with LS usually present with symptoms of acute pharyngitis and other nonspecific symptoms, such as fever. This may progress to a peritonsillar abscess, presenting as unilateral sore throat and odynophagia. The infection then progresses to internal jugular vein thrombophlebitis and sepsis, typically days after the primary infection, which may already be resolved. Thrombophlebitis often manifests as unilateral neck pain, headache, and swelling along the sternocleidomastoid muscle, and it is often mistaken for lymphadenitis. On admission, patients may present with signs of metastatic septic lesions to end organs. Pulmonary involvement, the most common metastatic site, can lead to symptoms such as cough, dyspnoea, pleuritic chest pain, and haemoptysis. Patients with joint involvement may present with septic arthritis and localized joint pain.^[3]

“Incomplete Lemierre syndrome” presents with metastatic infections in the absence of IJV thrombosis. Due to a dearth of research on atypical variations of the traditional Lemierre syndrome, cases lacking one of the hallmark clinical features often go unrecognized.^[4] This can lead to delays in diagnosis and suboptimal treatment strategies for incomplete LS. Since *F. necrophorum* can take 5 or more days to grow, a high degree of clinical suspicion is required for early diagnosis. LS has a mortality rate of up to 18% and diagnosis is critical.^[5] A once common and fatal syndrome became rare after the introduction of antibiotics; however, there has been a rise in its incidence in the last 30 years.^[2,3] The cause of this increase remains uncertain, but proposed factors include restricted antibiotic use, increasing antibiotic resistance, and a decrease in tonsillectomies.^[5] Hence, prompt treatment is crucial to prevent complications.

CONCLUSION

This case highlights an atypical presentation of Lemierre syndrome in a middle-aged male, characterized by metastatic infections and septicemia without radiologically confirmed internal jugular vein thrombosis. The diagnostic challenge posed by “incomplete Lemierre syndrome” emphasizes the importance of clinical suspicion, especially in patients with a recent history of oropharyngeal infections and systemic sepsis. Early recognition, prompt initiation of broad-spectrum antibiotics, and surgical intervention when necessary are crucial in improving patient outcomes. As the incidence of Lemierre syndrome rises, further research is needed to refine diagnostic criteria and optimize management strategies for its atypical presentations.

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